

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 3

Eight die in Philippines from red-tide molluscs

A state of emergency has been declared by Philippine President Fidel Ramos in Manila and four other provinces, due to the presence of red tides in various coastal regions and as a consequence of eight deaths caused by eating contaminated mussels.

Since June of this year, Philippine health authorities have banned the consumption of mussels, clams, and other bivalves on account of the extensive blooms of *Pyrodinium bahamense* which have coloured coastal waters red. Despite the ban, eight people have died and 150 have been hospitalized

after eating products contaminated with this microorganism.

The red tide covered about 90% of Manila Bay along the coasts of Batán, Papanga, Bulacan and Cavite.

The authorities state that fishermen in the zones where the consumption of mussels is prohibited are undergoing hardship due to a sudden fall in fish sales. The declaration of a state of emergency allows increased government aid to those affected.

Translated from Voz de Galicia (a Spanish newspaper) of 5 July 1992. Source EFE (news service), Manila.

Editor's note:

The dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense* has caused paralytic poisoning in Papua New Guinea, Brunei Darussalam, Sabah, and Guatemala, as well as in the Philippines, most commonly via shellfish but also via plankton-eating fish. Cases of PSP elsewhere in the western Pacific may be due to the same species. Jay Maclean of ICLARM⁽¹⁾ has pointed out 'the exact coincidence of major toxic red tides [in the western Pacific] between 1972 and 1987 with ENSO (El Niño-Southern Oscillation) events'.

Pyrodinium red tides were the topic of a management and training workshop held in Brunei Darussalam in May 1989. The proceedings are published as ICLARM contribution N° 585⁽¹⁾.

Artificial respiration saves two from fatal PSP in Canada

In April 1992, a party of seven were fishing in Kingcome Inlet, British Columbia, approximately 250 km north of Vancouver. On 19 April butter clams (*Saxidomus giganteus*) and cockle clams (*Clinocardium nuttalli*) were harvested from Moore Bay for an evening feast the following day. On the morning of the 20th a 54 year-old man decided to have some for breakfast. He threw them on hot coals just long enough for them to open slightly. He offered a butter clam to a 31 year-old companion who, after swallowing a "thumbnail-sized" bite (including the siphon tips) of a butter clam, decided that he didn't want the rest of it. The older man ate five in the period that the younger man went to fetch water.

Both began to experience tingling and numbness of the lips and mouth (paresthesia) within several minutes ("like having gone to the dentist") but not on initial contact, the effect spreading to their faces and fingers. Within 10 minutes the older man collapsed on the ground, vomiting, and the younger man was becoming severely paralysed. By 15 minutes the latter was unable to move and by 20 minutes was completely paralysed, unable to breath or

see (eyelids closed), total paralysis only coming later for the other (fifteen minutes into the flight). Throughout the whole episode both men were able to hear, including discussions among their friends as to whether there was any point in continuing artificial respiration!

Resuscitation was begun when it was noticed that they were turning blue, although showing no struggle for breath. Fortunately their companions knew industrial first aid and also had a radio. Coast guard helicopters picked them up after 45 minutes and took them first to a nearby town, Port McNeil, where they were treated for 6 hours, being intubated and given a gastric lavage. Then they were flown to Vancouver where they were connected to ventilators at Vancouver General Hospital. It was found that the older man had aspirated into one lung, a common problem with vomiting while becoming paralysed, the younger one also having done so to a much lesser extent. Atrial fibrillation was also present initially in the older man, probably the results of stress. Both patients were sedated.

(Cont'd on p. 5)

(1) Hallegraeff, G.M., J.L. Maclean (editors), 1989. Biology, epidemiology and management of *Pyrodinium* red tides. (Fisheries Dept., Brunei Darussalam, and ICLARM, Philippines).

Now available ...
see page 2

Cholera and the environment

For 30 years the search has gone on for an environmental reservoir for cholera to help explain seasonal oscillations. Dr Ventura and colleagues⁽¹⁾ demonstrate that the growth of *Vibrio cholerae* non-O1 on plant samples in sewage lagoons is associated with the seasonality of cholera in Peru. Colwell and her colleagues⁽²⁾ have also detected *V. cholerae* O1 on marine life, in non-culturable, viable states, and have demonstrated that this reservoir is sensitive to environmental changes.

Under unfavourable conditions, cholera bacteria become dormant, re-emerging to an infectious state with warming and nutrient availability. 'Hibernating' forms of *V. cholerae* co-exist with a wide variety of algae and plankton⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾, which are also responsive to changes in temperature, pH, salinity, and nutrition. Climatologists report unusually large algae and plankton blooms at sea, and plankton sampled in the harbour near Lima, Peru, are contaminated with *V. cholerae*⁽⁵⁾.

Phytoplankton and algae help modulate our climate⁽⁶⁾. They absorb atmospheric carbon (2 of the 7 billion metric tons released annually) and give off oxygen through photosynthesis; they scatter heat and light; and, through emission of volatile dimethylsulphide, help seed rain clouds. Marine plants are thus 'fertilized' by atmospheric CO₂ and by warming, and atmospheric CO₂ is increasing (now about 350 parts per million), mainly from fossil fuel combustion. Pacific waters began warming in late 1990⁽⁷⁾.

V. cholerae O1, biotype El Tor, serotype Inaba, may have arrived in the Americas with the bilge or ballast of a Chinese freighter⁽⁸⁾, and the studies of Drs. Faruque and Alberts with DNA probes⁽⁹⁾ suggest "genetic identity" for the strains causing epidemics in Bangladesh and the Americas. The unexpected intensity of the outbreak, which penetrated cities and towns along the Pacific coast in January and February 1991, is consistent with multiple entry points from marine life blooms, with fish, molluscs, and crustacea as vectors. The internal dissemination throughout South and Central America reflects the vulnerability of host de-

fenses, inadequacies in sanitation, clean water, and fuel supply, as well as the uncontrolled urbanization (eg, Lima's shanty-towns) generated by the economic collapse of the 1980s.

There is now convincing evidence for an environmental reservoir for cholera. Alterations, due to climatic change, in the distribution of water-based and vector-borne diseases have been predicted⁽¹⁰⁾⁽¹¹⁾, and the pattern of cholera in the Americas may represent the first detectable impact. Of the greenhouse gases, carbon emissions constitute 50%; and an international treaty to limit worldwide release was on the agenda for the UN Conference on the Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992. The changing distribution of old diseases (and the emergence of new ones) makes it essential that public health professionals and scientists participate centrally in planning developments.

By Paul R. Epstein, Cambridge Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA.

(1) Ventura, G. et al. *Lancet* 1992; 339: 937-938.

(2) Huq, A., Colwell, R.R. et al. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 1990; 56: 2370-73.

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(5) Tampin, M.L.; Parodi, C.C. *Lancet* 1991; 338: 1216-17.

(6) Williamson, P.; Gribbin, J. *New Sci.* 1991; March 16: 48-52.

(7) Kerr, R.A. *Science* 1992; 255:402.

(8) Anderson, C. *Nature* 1991; 354:255.

(9) Faruque, S.M.; Albert, J. *Lancet* 1992; 339:740-741.

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Editor's note:

From The Lancet (9 May 1992), Vol. 339: 1167-8, with permission. This aspect of algae, i.e. carrying the potential to cause severe and widespread harm to large communities, has not emerged in any of the toxic phytoplankton conferences.

International Workshop on Ciguatera Management

This workshop will be held 13-16 April 1993 on Bribie Island near Brisbane, Australia. The event, sponsored by the Australian Fisheries Research and Development Corporation and the Queensland Department of Primary Industries, will focus on current research that has implications on the management of ciguatera. It will include sessions on: (i) chemical and immunological aspects of the detection of ciguatera toxins, (ii) pharmacology and treatment, (iii) origin, and (iv) clinical aspects and epidemiology.

The workshop will include talks by invited speakers, discussion sessions and poster presentations. Further information can be obtained from: Workshop Secretariat, Southern Fisheries Centre, PO Box 76, Deception Bay, Queensland 4508, Australia. Tel: (61-7) 203 1444; fax: (61-7) 203 3517.

New publication

Now available are the *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Ciguatera, Puerto Rico, 1990*, edited by T.R. Tosteson and published by Polyscience Inc.; ISBN 0-921313-35-2; US \$60 plus shipping and handling charges. Those interested may send a request to: Polyscience Publications, 44 Scize Arpents, PO Box 148, Morin Heights, Quebec, Canada J0R 1H0. A limited number of copies are available for free to students, scientists and managers in developing countries, from: IOC Secretariat, att. Henrik Enevoldsen, UNESCO, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris Cedex 15, France.

Monitoring in Belfast Lough

Belfast Lough in Northern Ireland is a semi-enclosed, sheltered tidal inlet. The River Lagan, which enters the upper lough is heavily polluted with urban, industrial and agricultural waste. There are power stations on the south shore of the upper lough and on the north shore of the lower lough. The south side is a favoured residential area and has a high BOD (biological oxygen demand) requirement caused by accumulation of domestic wastes and the north has an industrial and residential mix (Carter, 1988). There are commercially harvested mussel beds along parts of both shores (Fig 1). No other shellfish are taken from the waters within the lough.

During the 1970's and early 1980's commercial shellfish beds in Northern Ireland coastal waters were regularly monitored for paralytic shellfish toxins by the mouse bioassay (Anon, 1984). A small number of these samples, mainly from within the lough, exceeded the accepted hazardous concentration of 400 mouse units (m.u.) per 100 g. After a series of negative results, routine testing ceased in the mid 1980's. A new programme, again based on the mouse bioassay, started in June 1990 following reports of toxic concentrations in mussels taken off the NE coast of England.

The first round of sampling revealed a maximum concentration of 480 m.u. in one sample of mussels collected from the north shore of the lough. Contemporaneous samples from other areas in the lough and more widely around the Northern Ireland coast were negative. Following these results a selective health warning was

Fig. 2: Paralytic shellfish poison survey, Belfast Lough, 1990.

Fig. 1: Outline of mussel beds in Belfast Lough.

issued and commercial harvesting ceased.

A more extensive survey, based on weekly sampling of recognised coastal shellfish beds, was instituted and continued until the concentration in all samples fell below 400 m.u. During the survey detectable toxin concentrations occurred only within the upper lough, first off the north and subsequently off the south shore. The elevated concentrations peaked at 5496 m.u. and remained above the hazardous level until early August (Fig 2). The toxin peaks of the north and south shores appear to be similar but the latter increased later and decreased more rapidly. Samples of winkles, crabs, limpets and oysters collected from harvesting areas around the coast were consistently negative for PSP toxin. Additional samples of scallops were taken when concentrations above 400 m.u. were confirmed in scallops from the coast of Scotland. There was no detectable toxin in these samples.

A similar collection and testing programme was maintained in 1991. Toxin was detected only from within the lough and the maximum was 257 m.u. per 100 g in one sample collected from the north shore of the lough. Monitoring in 1992 to date has also failed

to detect PSP toxin.

Information collected on the local climatic conditions in 1990 and 1991 show that there were less hours of sunlight, air temperatures were lower, and there was less rainfall in May and June in 1991. The wind speed was higher from May to July in 1991. Within the lough the available data suggest that the water temperature off the north shore is consistently lower (difference: 1 to 3 degrees Centigrade). There were no reports of visible blooms in the lough during either year. If such had occurred it is probable that the event would have been recorded. The area is regularly overflowed by commercial aircraft arriving at the Harbour airport, ships frequently cross the lough to enter the harbour and there are several yacht clubs and marinas using the inshore areas.

These results suggest that, in the coastal waters of Northern Ireland, PSP toxins occur only within Belfast Lough. If this is confirmed by further studies over a more extensive period, then selective sampling from this area may be an effective means of regularly monitoring to detect PSP risk at an early stage.

By W.J. McCaughey and J.N. Campbell, Veterinary Sciences Division, Department of Agriculture, N. I., Stony Road, Belfast, BT4 3SD, Northern Ireland, U.K.

References:

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Intergovernmental panel recommends concerted HAB action

At its first session (Paris, 23-25 June 1992) a joint IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) reviewed IOC's activities on harmful algae and the Programme Plan for HABs as it was prepared at the IOC-SCOR Workshop in Newport last year. Fourteen countries were represented. The Panel serves as an intergovernmental mechanism guiding the international HAB programme and dealing with resource gaps.

Based on its review, the Panel concluded that the information network and training elements of the programme need more emphasis and visibility. The revised Programme Plan consists of educational, scientific and operational elements.

The Panel agreed on a set of recommendations for the further development and implementation of the HAB Programme, which are summarized as follows:

Structural

- The modified Programme Plan on Harmful Algal Blooms suggested by the IOC-SCOR Workshop on Programme Development on HABs should be adopted by the IOC Assembly (Paris, March 1993).
- An IOC-FAO Programme Office for HABs should be established in accordance with the revised Terms of Reference.
- An IOC-FAO group of experts is needed to guide and advise IOC and FAO on scientific and managerial problems relevant to the HAB Programme. Membership and terms of reference should be elaborated by the two sponsors in consultation with the Panel.
- The joint IOC-FAO ad hoc Intergovernmental Panel on HABs should continue its work until otherwise decided by IOC and FAO, the terms of reference remaining unchanged.

Action by Member States

- The promotion of the HAB Programme by:
 - a) identifying (i) national resources and resource personnel to support the programme planning process and, if possible, locate resources to support their participation in the necessary meetings; (ii) training needs; (iii) institutions and organizations willing to operate, co-sponsor, and/or host training

activities, both in developed countries with visiting students, and in developing countries with visiting and resident staff; (iv) personnel and organizations to interact with, and provide material for this newsletter;

b) obtaining national support for: (i) WESTPAC⁽¹⁾ and IOCARIBE⁽²⁾ programmes, for the States in these regions; (ii) the Global Environment Facility and UNDP⁽³⁾ activities on harmful algae; and

c) encouraging PICES⁽⁴⁾ to include HAB activities in its programme formulation.

Intersecretariat action

The IOC Secretariat, in co-operation

with the FAO Secretariat and the Chairman of the Panel, should: (i) continue the planning process; (ii) solicit offers from Member States to provide support for the establishment of the HAB Programme Office; (iii) seek expansion of participation in the HAB Programme by other international organizations; (iv) increase the interaction and participation of programme participants in other IOC activities, in particular TEMA⁽⁵⁾, GIPME⁽⁶⁾ and GOOS⁽⁷⁾; (v) prepare a training programme based on identified training needs; (vi) continue the publication of this newsletter; (vii) proceed with the publication of an updated and expanded version of the

(Cont'd on p. 7)

An appeal from Rumania

During the last three decades, very dense algal blooms have been a regular feature in Rumanian coastal waters (Black Sea). As well, some occurrences offshore have been noted.

The most important species involved, and concentrations of cells reached (in $10^6 l^{-1}$) are *Skeletonema costatum* (18-97), *Cyclotella caspia* (14-28), *Nitzschia delicatissima* (4-21), *Prorocentrum cordatum* (50-197), *Heterocapsa triquetra* (11-40) and *Apedinella radians* (1-21). Toxicity has not been identified, but increased DOM (dissolved organic matter) and ammonia levels, anoxia, and fish and shellfish mortalities are com-

mon events in summer, especially in association with *Prorocentrum cordatum* blooms.

Rumanian scientists involved in scientific and monitoring programmes centred on these problems would welcome international collaboration in the study of: (1) microflagellate taxonomy, (2) development of culture techniques for physiological studies, and (3) analysis of long term data sets of phytoplankton and accompanying physical and chemical information.

Anyone interested should contact: Pia Elena Mihnea, Rumanian Marine Research Institute, Bd. Mamaia N^o 300, 8700 Constanta, Rumania.

Dead fish and crustaceans on strand line (measure marks/m²). Photo: Pia-Elena Mihnea.

(Cont'd from p. 1, 'PSP in Canada')

The younger man was totally paralysed for 24 hours, unconscious for 48 hours and showed neurological symptoms (difficulty with sight co-ordination and walking) for a further 48 hours. He was released after 6 days. The older man was in intensive care for longer, largely as a result of the complications of his condition and was only released on 29 April.

The only after-effect experienced by both men was pneumonia, more severe in the older man, due to the aspiration into their lungs. The vomitus was not retained for testing but the uneaten remaining shellfish was found to contain up to 10,000 µg toxin per 100 g meat (R. Chiang, Fisheries Inspection Branch, Department of Fisheries and Oceans, pers. comm.).

It is difficult to estimate the toxic doses received by the men in view of the vomiting and chewing of siphon tips, partial cooking, as well as the mix of clams with cockles (the latter had lower toxicity) but one can estimate the possible maximum ingested.

The five clams eaten, assuming an average flesh weight of 35 g, probably contained a total of at least 17,500 µg. In the butter clam the siphons contain as much as 77% of the total toxin (Quayle, 1969) and so the part consumed could have contained more than 2,500 µg. Weights of the older and younger man were 87.5 and 73 kg respectively. Based on these considerations the doses for two could have been 200 µg and 35 µg per kg respectively. Similar estimates have been made by Ewan Todd (Health & Welfare Canada, Health Protection Branch). In view of the extremely rapid and severe onset in the younger man it seems likely that this is an underestimate in his case. Alcohol, known to add to the severity, had been freely consumed the previous evening and the older man had some rum in his morning coffee.

Unfortunately no plankton samples were taken prior to, or during this episode, and so the identity of the causative organism is unknown. On the basis of general distributional data (Taylor, 1984) we suspect that it was due to *Alexandrium (Protogonyaulax) catenella*. Samples taken two weeks later, courtesy of R. Forbes, Institute of Ocean Sciences, did not contain *Alexandrium* cells.

Several significant features of this event stand out. Although the area where the toxicity occurred (Fisheries zone 12) has consistently been an early

Red-Tide Research and Monitoring Programme in South East Asia

EVS Consultants Ltd. is pleased to have been selected by the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) to be the Canadian Executing Agency (CEA) for a five-year project in the southeast Asia region, including: Thailand, Brunei Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines and Singapore. The project is aimed at red-tide response programmes and the establishment of environmental criteria for protection of marine resources. The objectives are to enhance ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations) marine science capabilities and human resources through the development of technical studies on red tides and other environmental concerns. This will be pursued through an institutional strengthening strategy designed to develop, among ASEAN marine science institutions and researchers, a capacity to pursue regional environmental management objectives on a long-term basis. Technical support by

Canadian and ASEAN marine science professionals for the technical studies will be complemented by formal post-graduate training, practical attachments, workshops and seminars.

EVS Consultants is presently developing research priorities for red-tide projects, in conjunction with the ASEAN countries. We would be pleased to receive inputs/comments from other researchers in this area, especially from the six ASEAN countries, with respect to possible cooperative research activities. Please contact: (a) Mr Peter Nix, EVS Consultants Ltd., 195 Pemberton Avenue, North Vancouver, B.C., Canada, V7P 2R4. Fax: (1-604) 662 8548; (b) Mr Dwight Watson in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Fax: (1-603) 293 6146; or (c) Dr Max Taylor, Dept of Oceanography, University of B.C, Vancouver, B.C., Canada V6N 2L7. Fax: (1-604) 822 6091.

By Peter G. Nix, EVS Consultants.

location for toxin increase (Fisheries Inspection data for six years) such high concentrations are approximately a month earlier than might be expected. The west coast is currently experiencing a waning El Niño effect. Based on this and a 6–8 year cycle, 1992 was predicted to be worse than usual for PSP (Taylor, 1992).

The men undoubtedly would have died had it not been for (a) the ability to perform resuscitation by their companions, (b) possession of a radio while in a remote area, (c) knowledgeable and prompt responses by the Coast Guard, (d) steps to reduce the effects at Port McNeil, and (e) use of modern hospital ventilators. These are the first cases in British Columbia to survive under such circumstances. They show that resuscitation should always be performed as long as there is the slightest hope of reaching a ventilator. They also confirm observations from sublethal exposures that there do not appear to be lasting after-effects.

This episode also stresses the need for greater public education, even on a coast where PSP is endemic (records extend back to 1793, the last fatality being in 1981). None of the fishermen were more than slightly aware of the risks involved, the potential lethality,

the lack of antidote, the most toxic parts of the shellfish, etc. The current shellfish monitoring programme can only protect in a general, statistical way. Samples taken by inspectors the same day elsewhere in the Inlet and vicinity had levels reaching 440 µg, illustrating the well-known problem of small scale variability. Closures, other than blanket regional bans (which are often disregarded by locals), are always after the fact and cannot protect individuals collecting shellfish at the same time as Fisheries Inspectors.

By F.J.R. 'Max' Taylor

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Editor's note:

Max Taylor pointed out in his letter that 'these may be the first people to survive unquestionably fatal doses'. Does anybody know of others?

Blue-Green Algae in Australia

In November 1991 what has been described as the world's largest freshwater algae bloom occurred in outback Australia. (Further details can be found in the article by Dr. Gustaaf Hallegraeff on the opposite page). A stretch of the Darling River over one thousand kilometres long experienced a bloom dominated by *Anabaena* species. During the last few years the public in many regions of the country have been sensitized to the issue of cyanobacteria in recreational, irrigation, agricultural and potable waters. The magnitude of the Darling River bloom focussed attention across Australia on the problems of algal blooms and the broader issues of water quality and toxin contamination from cyanobacteria.

Blooms of cyanobacteria, or blue-green algae, are not new to Australia, nor is the recognition of the toxic effects; Francis (1878) reported stock deaths resulting from a cyanobacterial bloom (*Nodularia spumigena*) in Lake Alexandrina (South Australia). More recently the risk to public health has been identified (e.g. Falconer *et al*, 1983 and Hawkins *et al*, 1985). It is only in recent years though that this understanding has been translated into the management of water systems. The summer of 1989-90 saw the closure of several water storages in southeastern Australia due to cyanobacterial blooms. These included storages for irrigation, recreation and potable supplies. Blooms also occur on slow-flowing rivers. The following summers have seen an increase in the number of storages and water supplies closed or affected by cyanobacteria, probably due not to an increase in bloom occurrence but to a greater awareness of the potential risk and recognition of the issues involved.

The closure of water supplies causes significant disruptions to local communities. More often than not the towns affected have had a single source of water. The need to develop contingency plans for dealing with water supplies during algal blooms resulted in the formation of interdepartmental working groups in some States. The leap in the public profile of algal blooms that came from the Darling River incident resulted in a series of Task Forces being established at both the State and Federal levels of government, to bring together the various

agencies involved in the water industry in order to minimize the future incidence and impact of algal blooms. Out of these gatherings of expertise it has become apparent that there are many unanswered questions on the causes, management and effects of algal blooms that need to be resolved if the situation is to improve. The Australian Water Resources Council (AWRC), the peak forum for the water industry, established a National Project Manager for Algal Bloom Research to provide a co-ordinated, focussed approach to resolving these issues. At present, the additional demands for further research into algal blooms have to be accommodated in existing budgets. There is some hope that the identification of knowledge gaps on a national scale will promote the allocation of additional resources towards algal bloom issues.

In order to reduce the occurrence of blooms in the longer term, attention is being focussed on nutrient sources and inputs to aquatic systems together with management of flow regimes. This approach is similar to that adopted in other countries, but Australia does have some characteristics that affect the dynamics of aquatic systems and the potential for control of algal blooms. The landscape of Australia is dominated by old erodible soils, and waters are generally turbid due to the suspension of fine clays. These clays provide binding sites for phosphorus, which means that a significant proportion of the total phosphorus load is not readily available to biota. For example, at one site on the Broken River in Victoria, turbidity ranges from 5 to 110 NTU for a suspended solid level of 10 to 55 mg/L and total phosphorus ranges from 0.01 to 0.1 mg/L of which 0.003 to 0.02 mg/L is filtered reactive phosphorus (Harrison *et al* 1990). The suspended clays provide a transport mechanism for phosphorus and an additional sink both within the water column and in areas of deposition. Remobilisation can occur from these sinks. Coupled with these problems are climatic factors. Australia is the driest continent, and even the wetter parts of temperate Australia have high variability in rainfall. The natural pattern of streamflow includes droughts and floods and it is not uncommon for a dry summer to be broken by torrential

Anabaena sp.

downpours. This feature encourages the transport of nutrients to aquatic systems. Cullen (pers. comm.) has found in a study of one small catchment that 61% of the phosphorus and 41% of the water moved down a creek in 1% of the time. The variability of runoff and general aridity of Australia have resulted in major constructions to store and manage water so that the flow regimes of rivers now bear little resemblance to natural conditions.

While the Australian cyanobacterial blooms may have local characteristics, the overall mechanisms and impacts are common with eutrophication internationally. The Australian research effort intends to be complementary to research in other countries. The AWRC National Project Manager for Algal Bloom Research, Dr Phillip Johnstone, would like to hear from any organization or individuals involved in aspects of cyanobacterial bloom research. He can be contacted at: Department of Water Resources, 35 Spring St., Melbourne, Victoria 3000, Australia. Tel: (61-3) 651 3648; fax: (61-3) 651 3989.

By Phillip Johnstone, AWRC National Project Manager, Algal Bloom Research.

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Massive Bloom of Toxic Blue-Green Algae in Australian Rivers

In mid-November 1991 the largest riverine toxic blue-green algal bloom (mainly *Anabaena circinalis*), ever recorded anywhere in the world, occurred in the Darling/Barwon River system in New South Wales, Australia. Cell counts exceeded 105 cell/ml and most sites tested were found to contain high concentrations of both hepatotoxins and neurotoxins. The bloom contaminated supplies of drinking water for country towns and killed hundreds of sheep and cattle as well as wildlife which had drunk affected water. Farmers in affected areas were forced to drive hundreds of kilometres to satisfy their families requirements for drinking water. Fish kills resulted from the generation of anoxic conditions, and significant economic losses were suffered by tourism and recreation. A state of emergency was declared and this was only lifted in late December after the first heavy rains of the season reduced the algal bloom through flushing and increased turbidity.

Toxic blooms of freshwater and brackish water blue-green algae are not new to Australia. This phenomenon was first recorded from Lake Alexandria in South Australia in 1878 (caused by *Nodularia spumigena*), and

in 1959 one of the worst blooms in Lake Bonney, South Australia (probably a mixture of *Anabaena circinalis* and *Microcystis aeruginosa*) killed 300 sheep, 5 cattle and a horse. What is new, however, is the enormous extent of the 1991 bloom, stretching 1200 km through the Darling River system from Queensland in the north through New South Wales where it joins the Murray River in Victoria and South Australia. The river's catchment area covers 1/7 of the continent of Australia, that is, as large as France and Spain together. The bloom was continuous throughout the length of the river but this was not due to transport because the flow was too low to allow for this.

The latest *Anabaena circinalis* bloom has been blamed on eutrophication by sewage from townships (a population of 600,000 people), run-off of agricultural fertilizers (especially super phosphates) and from wasted cattle feedlot, in combination with high summer temperatures and low river flow rates. Flow rates in the Darling River were only 1/30 of normal due to both drought conditions and significant diversions (up to 60% of total flow) for irrigation of cotton fields. The loss of macrophytes along the river banks in the past 10 years (reduced

nutrient removal) and the introduction of European carp (increased sediment nutrient release due to resuspension of sediments) may also have contributed. A Senate Inquiry into the toxic algal bloom was instigated and a National Task Force was created to coordinate the research activities of a large number of overlapping water authorities, and Commonwealth and University scientists. (See accompanying article by Dr Phillip Johnstone.)

By Gustaaf M. Hallegraef, Department of Plant Science, University of Tasmania, Hobart, Tasmania, Australia.

(Cont'd from p. 4, 'Panel')

International Directory of Experts in Toxic and Harmful Algal Blooms and Their Effects on Fisheries and Public Health; (viii) proceed with the publication of a manual which compiles widely different information on the taxonomy, toxicology, and epidemiology of harmful algal blooms, and which should be distributed freely to developing countries; and (ix) support national and international conferences related to harmful algae.

It should be the task of the IOC Secretariat, the Intergovernmental HAB Panel, and national research, management and administrative institutions to achieve these goals in concert. Readers may address a request for a copy of the outline of the HAB Programme Plan (IOC Workshop Report No. 80) to: IOC Secretariat, attn: Henrik Enevoldsen, UNESCO, 1 rue Miollis, 75732 Paris cedex 15, France.

- (1) WESTPAC = IOC's Programme Group for the Western Pacific Region.
- (2) IOCARIBE = IOC Sub-commission for the Caribbean and Adjacent Regions.
- (3) UNDP = United Nations Development Programme.
- (4) PICES = Pacific International Council for the Exploration of the Sea.
- (5) TEMA = Training, Education and Mutual Assistance (IOC).
- (6) GIPME = Global Investigation of Pollution in the Marine Environment (IOC and UNEP).
- (7) GOOS = Global Ocean Observing System (IOC, WMO and UNEP).

2nd Luso-Spanish Meeting on Toxic Phytoplankton, Shellfish Toxicity, and Prevention Measures

Held 10-12 March 1992 in Lisbon, Portugal, this meeting focussed on the management of the marine environment and the seafood industry in the region. Sponsored by INIP (the Portuguese National Fisheries Research Institute), the event aimed in particular to: (i) establish research priorities more in line with current knowledge and the concerns of aquaculture, fisheries and public health; (ii) develop and improve methods to minimize the environmental and economic consequences of harmful algal blooms (HABs); (iii) enhance the flow of information between the two countries (Portugal and Spain); and (iv) standardize, as far as possible, the national monitoring programmes both for toxic species and toxin detection in seafoods. Also discussed was the creation of a regional programme to understand the causes, predict the occurrences and mitigate the effects of HABs.

Among the main topics of discussion were:

- Toxic algae occurrences and interaction with physico-chemical parameters in the region.
- DSP⁽¹⁾ and PSP⁽²⁾ toxins, accumulation by shellfish, detection methods, permitted levels and quarantines.
- The Iberian coast as a pilot region for the study of HABs.

During the meeting, workshops were held on the main topics in order to standardize methodologies and to discuss the preparation of an interdisciplinary international programme to study the dynamics of HABs.

Agreement was reached on methodologies for toxin detection. Protocols for the mouse bioassay for DSP and PSP were written and a resolution passed to present them to the European

Economic Community (EEC) Commission. The latter action was in response to an agenda item of an Expert Meeting on 25 March 1992 in Brussels, which called for: "Preparation of a draft for methods, analytical tolerances and sampling plans on mouse bioassay in order to detect biotoxins". Periodical intercalibration exercises were agreed upon between Spain and Portugal. It was agreed that the Iberian coast would serve as a suitable region for an interdisciplinary international pilot study on the dynamics of harmful algal blooms, and that a proposal for such a study should be presented at the forthcoming meeting of the ICES-IOC Study Group on the Dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms, 7-9 April 1992, Vigo, Spain (see *HAN* No. 2).

Red-tide specialists in Portugal and Spain are relatively advanced in the creation of a regional programme, but considerable effort is still required to strengthen communication and increase interaction and collaboration in order to concert efforts and maximize results.

The need for research funds was emphasized. As well, priority was given to the necessity of closer collaboration with national planning and policy agencies, in particular to convince them that HAB problems are severe, growing and of high priority with respect to other competing national needs.

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- (1) DSP= Diarrhetic shellfish poisoning.
(2) PSP= Paralytic shellfish poisoning.

Future events

NOVEMBER 92

8th International IUPAC Symposium on Mycotoxins and Phycotoxins, 8-12 November, Stouffer Presidente Hotel, Mexico City, Mexico. *Contact:* Symposium Secretariat, VIII International IUPAC, Insurgentes Sur 3700 - C, Apartado Postal 101-63, 04530 Mexico DF, Mexico. Tel: (52-5) 550 58 83; fax: (52-5) 548 82 07.

APRIL 93

International Workshop on Ciguatera Management, 13-16 April, Bribie Island, Australia. *Contact:* Workshop Secretariat, Southern Fisheries Centre, PO Box 76, Deception Bay, Queensland 4508, Australia. Tel: (61-7) 203 1444; fax: (61-7) 203 3517.

OCTOBER 93

SIXTH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

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HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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